

Kinetic and isotherm analyses for adsorption of a triphenylmethane dye onto jackfruit peel carbon

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A carbon adsorbent derived from jackfruit peel was used for the removal of a triphenylmethane dye, malachite green dye, from aqueous solution. Kinetic and isotherm data were modeled with various kinetic (Lagergren's pseudo-first order, Ritchie second order and modified Ritchie second order equations) and isotherm (Freundlich, Langmuir, Redlich-Peterson and Sips equations) model equations and the results obtained were suitably interpreted. The kinetic results were also fitted with the Weber-Morris model to test the role of diffusion and identify different stages of adsorption.

This study is a part of our continuing interest¹ in the search for indigenous, inexpensive low cost materials to study their capability for the removal of dyes and metals from aqueous solution. In the present investigation jackfruit peel, an agricultural waste byproduct, was tested after treatment with sulphuric acid for its efficiency in removing malachite green, a triphenylmethane dye, from aqueous solution by batch adsorption process. Fruit of jack (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) is one of the popular fruits in India, where the total area under this fruit is about 13460 hectares². Significant amount of peel (approximately, 2714–11800 kg per tree per year) is discarded as agricultural waste, as apart from its use as a table fruit, it is popular in many culinary preparations².

Results and discussion

Batch kinetic experiments performed indicate that the uptake of dye increased progressively with time; removal being rapid in the initial stages of contact time and attains equilibrium in 60 min for 20 mg dm⁻³ and 180 min for both 40 and 60 mg dm⁻³. With increase in dye concentration from 20 to 60 mg dm⁻³, the amount of dye adsorbed increased from 77.60 to 167.60 mg g⁻¹. This is due to the increase in driving force of the concentration gradient as the initial dye concentration increases.

Initially, the kinetic results were modeled with Lagergren's pseudo-first order model³ by nonlinear optimization method using GNUPLOT computer program (Version 3.7 for MS Windows) and was found to show a better fit with the experimental values (0.97 to 0.99) only in the initial stages of adsorption (covering a maximum of four experimental points) and thereafter deviates over the entire period of adsorption.

$$q_t = q_e [1 - \exp(-k_1 t)] \quad (1)$$

where q_e and q_t are the amounts of dye adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t (mg g⁻¹), respectively and k_1 is the first order rate constant (min⁻¹). It was also reported elsewhere^{3,4} that the Lagergren's pseudo-first order equation does not fit well the whole range of adsorption period and is generally applicable over the initial stages of adsorption processes. Several researchers, though got a poor fit for pseudo-first order equation, did not comment on this observation. Some authors⁵ proposed that a multiple series of pseudo-first order reactions to occur. A biphasic Lagergren plot was reported for the adsorption of lead onto lignite⁶. However, none of the researchers tested any other kinetic models.

In the present study the kinetic results were also fitted with second order kinetic models⁷ like Ritchie second order and modified Ritchie second order models and compared with the fit obtained with pseudo-first order model.

$$q_t = q_e \left\{ 1 - \left[\frac{1}{1 + k_2 t} \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$q_t = q_e \left\{ 1 - \left[\frac{1}{\beta_2 + k_2 t} \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

where, β_2 is a constant that represents initial particle loading and k_2 is the second order rate constant. The fitted curves of the kinetic models along with the experimental data are shown in Fig. 1. To measure the degree of fitness of the models with the experimental data, correlation coefficient, r^2 and sum of the squares of errors, SSE, were computed

Fig. 1. Fitted curves of the kinetic models with experimental data : (■) experimental data, 40 mg dm⁻³; (▲) experimental data, 60 mg dm⁻³; (*) experimental data, 20 mg dm⁻³; (-----) pseudo-first order model; (---) Ritchie second order model; (—) modified Ritchie second order model.

and are reported in Table 1.

$$SSE = \sum (q_i - q_p)^2 \tag{4}$$

where, q_i and q_p are the experimental and theoretical adsorption capacity data, respectively. It is evident from Table 1 that the modified Ritchie second order model predicted the experimental kinetic values more closely than that predicted by Ritchie second order and pseudo-first order models, as evidenced by the higher r^2 and lower SSE values obtained for modified Ritchie second order model. The fitted parameters of modified Ritchie second order equation are reported in Table 2.

Table 1. Degree of fitness of kinetic models based on SSE and r^2 values

Initial dye concentration (mg dm ⁻³)	Pseudo-first order		Ritchie second order		Modified Ritchie second order	
	r^2	SSE	r^2	SSE	r^2	SSE
20	0.93	170.17	0.99	17.84	0.99	10.96
40	0.70	2603.74	0.86	150.10	0.99	5.91
60	0.74	3114.04	0.88	1331.39	0.99	66.88

The kinetic results were also fitted with the Weber-Morris⁸ equation to test the role of diffusion (as the rate controlling step) in the adsorption process and to identify different stages of adsorption.

$$q_t = K_p t^{1/2} \tag{5}$$

If intraparticle diffusion is solely the rate-determining step, a linear plot passing through the origin would be obtained and the intraparticle diffusion parameter, K_p , could be estimated from the slope of the straight line. But many authors⁹ have reported multilinearity for such plot. Fig. 2 shows the Weber-Morris plot for the adsorption of malachite green onto JPC. The plot shows three distinct portions. The first sharper portion is the instantaneous adsorption stage or external surface adsorption. The Fig. 2 depicts that the initial portion of dye uptake due to film diffusion could not be followed experimentally due to the fastness of dye adsorption and that the boundary layer effect is important up to 5 min. This may be due to the fine particle size of JPC (44–89 μm) taken for study. The second linear portion is the gradual adsorption stage attributed to intraparticle diffusion effect (indicated by dotted lines). The third portion is final equilibrium stage where the intraparticle diffusion rate starts

Table 2. Fitted parameters of modified Ritchie second order model and intraparticle diffusion rate constant

Initial dye concentration (mg dm ⁻³)	Modified Ritchie second order model parameters			Intraparticle diffusion rate constant (mg g ⁻¹ min ^{-1/2})	
	q_e (mg g ⁻¹)	β_2	k_2 (min ⁻¹)	K_{p1}	K_{p2}
20	80.52	1.17	0.59	9.61	1.82
40	168.68	1.57	0.05	9.79	3.40
60	179.41	1.55	0.05	9.59	4.91

Fig. 2. Weber-Morris intraparticle diffusion plots : (■) 40 mg dm⁻³; (▲) 60 mg dm⁻³; (*) 20 mg dm⁻³

to slow down due to extremely low adsorbate concentrations left in the solution. Wu *et al.*¹⁰ have reported a similar observation for the adsorption of reactive dye and humic acid on chitosans. The intraparticle diffusion stage (second linear portion) does not pass through the origin indicating that the overall rate is not controlled solely by intraparticle diffusion. The rate parameter (K_p) for intraparticle diffusion stages (second and third stages) were obtained from the slope of each stage and are termed as K_{p1} and K_{p2} , respectively (Table 2).

To confirm the above mentioned results, pore diffusion coefficient, D_p , was calculated,

$$D_p = 0.03 \frac{r_0^2}{t_{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

where, r_0 is the radius of the adsorbent (cm) and $t_{1/2}$ is the time for half change (s). The D_p values obtained were 4.67×10^{-9} , 4.01×10^{-9} and $4.03 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for initial dye concentrations of 20, 40 and 60 mg dm^{-3} , respectively. The D_p values obtained ($10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) were in between the range specified¹¹ for film (10^{-6} to $10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and pore diffusion processes (10^{-11} to $10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) to be rate controlling in an adsorption process. This indicates that film and pore diffusion processes in combination control the adsorption of malachite green dye on JPC.

Equilibrium data, commonly known as adsorption isotherms are basic requirements for the design of adsorption systems. The equilibrium results obtained with a range of dye concentrations were fitted with 2-parameter, Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm models¹² and 3-parameter, Redlich-Peterson and Sips combination isotherm models¹³. The r^2 and SSE values computed are 0.74 and 1780.78, 0.94 and 439.48, 0.94 and 391.33 and 0.98 and 157.58, respectively, for Freundlich, Langmuir, Redlich-Peterson and Sips isotherm models, which reveals that the Sips combination isotherm model gives a better fit among the isotherm models tested and the fitted parameters of Sips model obtained for the present adsorption system is

$$q_e = \frac{888.20C_e^{3.43}}{1 + 5.55C_e^{3.43}} \quad (7)$$

Using the best fit Sips model, the volume of wastewater that could be treated was determined. If a wastewater contains 10 mg dm^{-3} of malachite green dye, 1 g of JPC can treat about 16.0 L of wastewater. The essential characteristics of Langmuir isotherm can be expressed by a dimensionless constant separation factor called equilibrium parameter, R_L ¹⁴, which is defined as $R_L = 1/(1 + bC_0)$, where

b is the Langmuir constant and C_0 is the initial dye concentration. The value of R_L indicates the shape of isotherm to be either unfavourable ($R_L > 1$) or linear ($R_L = 1$) or favourable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$). The R_L values obtained were in the range of 0.0048 to 0.0238, which indicate that the adsorption of malachite green dye on JPC is favourable ($0 < R_L < 1$) for the concentration range studied.

Mechanism : The carbon prepared by sulphuric acid treatment is also called as 'sulphuric acid activated carbon' or 'ion exchange activated carbon'¹⁵. Carbon prepared by sulphuric acid treatment have been reported¹⁶ to have the capability of decolourizing dyes^{17,18} and possess ion exchange properties^{18,19}. Accordingly, it is proposed that while carbonizing jackfruit peel using sulphuric acid, sulphonic groups ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) may be introduced through sulphonation, which are capable of exchanging cationic dyes present in solution. Hence this type of carbon shows both adsorptive and ion exchange properties.

Further studies on the adsorption efficiency of jackfruit peel carbon on other environmentally challenging basic dyes along with their nature of binding are underway.

Experimental

Preparation and characterization of jackfruit peel carbon : Peel of ripe jackfruit was collected from local shops and was air-dried, after removing the carpel fibers. The chopped pieces of peel was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (sp. gr. 1.84) in a weight ratio of 1 : 1.8 (peel : acid) and the resulting carbonised product was kept in an air-oven maintained at $160 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 h followed by washing with water until free of excess acid and dried at $105 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. The carbon product obtained from jackfruit peel (JPC) was ground and the portion retained between 44 and 89 μm sieves was used. The JPC was characterized for pH (7.24), moisture content (18.70%), bulk density (0.76 g cm^{-3}), ash content (5.10%), water and acid soluble matter (1.40 and 10.20%), decolourising power (127.50 mg g^{-1}), iron content (0.07%) according to ISI methods²⁰. Ion exchange capacity (1.01 meq. g^{-1}) and ash analysis ($\text{SiO}_2 = 16.0\%$, $\text{Na}_2\text{O} = 4.03\%$, $\text{K}_2\text{O} = 0.72\%$, $\text{CaO} = 16.6\%$ and $\text{MgO} = 33.8\%$) were determined as per the standard procedures²¹. Surface area ($131.73 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) was measured using direct reading Carlo Erba Sorptomatic-1800 by assuming that the adsorbed nitrogen forms a monolayer and posses a molecular cross sectional area of 16 \AA .

Adsorption experiments : Malachite green dye was supplied by Bayer Ltd. Batch mode adsorption study was carried out by agitating a known weight of JPC with dye solu-

tion of desired concentration at pH 6.0 and at room temperature ($32 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$) in a mechanical shaker (250 rpm). After the defined time intervals, samples were withdrawn from the shaker, centrifuged and the supernatant solution was analysed for residual dye concentration using a Jasco Double Beam Spectrophotometer (UVIDEC-430B) at 620 nm. Kinetic study was carried out by taking three dye concentrations viz. 20, 40 and 60 mg dm^{-3} and agitating with the JPC dose of 0.25 g dm^{-3} at predetermined intervals of time. For isotherm study initial dye concentration ranging from 20 to 100 mg dm^{-3} was agitated with a fixed JPC dose (0.25 g dm^{-3}) until the equilibrium was reached. Experiments were repeated at least three times and mean values are reported. Standard deviations and analytical errors were calculated and the maximum error was $\pm 5\%$.

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